

Redefining the Teaching-Learning Process by Employing Blended Learning Designs in Education: An Emerging Trend in Pedagogy

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Abstract The cognitive abilities of every individual are different. Every Individual learns differently and therefore needs differentiated instruction. Alone the traditional teaching can't appeal to the senses of modern learners. They require the components of traditional as well as modern teaching. Blended learning can fulfill the demand of modern learners as it involves the components of traditional as well as modern teaching. Blended learning designs use the technology in the teaching-learning process but also acknowledge the traditional learning methods. The NEP 2020 also accentuated that in the age of digital and online learning, we should not ignore the face to face learning, therefore the adoption of Blended learning design is recommended by the Policy. The aim of Collaborative and co-operative learning can be accomplished with the help of this design. It gives space to the learners for the interaction with teachers as well as peers. The active Participation of the learners can be increased with the help of blended learning designs which otherwise is challenging in traditional classrooms. The complex concepts can be made easy through blended learning designs. These designs of learning leave the long lasting effect on the learners. There are various models of Blended learning which can be used according to the different learning contexts. The new collaborative blended learning models have also emerged in the field of education. This paper aimed to explore the importance of Blended learning designs in the teaching-learning process. Further, this paper will also highlight the contribution of Blended learning designs in promoting cooperative and active learning. The study will also reveal that how cooperative blended learning strategies will promote critical thinking and insightful learning.

Keywords: Blended Learning, Cooperative Learning, Differentiated Instruction

Introduction

In the present era of educational technology blended learning is an important contribution in the field of teaching and learning. Blended mode of learning is the opportunity for the learners to learn from both online materials and in the traditional setup of face-to-face learning. To make a learning environment positive teachers should have the required ability to encourage students to more contribute to their learning actions (Donnelly, 2010) and they must find a technique that helps them to interact socially in a cooperative manner (Liu, 2010; Delialioğlu, 2012). In blended learning, teachers can spend much of their time interacting with the students rather than lecturing during face-to-face class time. Teachers can use online delivery of content with the use of technology to reinforce the learning in students. NEP 2020 also suggested various models of blended learning in the teaching-learning process. It suggested the combination of traditional learning with the informative and intelligent use of technology. Today, in the time of pandemic blended learning plays an important role in disseminating knowledge among learners. Teachers can use the blended model of teaching-learning with the use of cooperative learning strategies to make learning interesting and productive. In the present era of information and communication technology in which learning is

dominated by digital devices for making the learning effective, blended learning becomes a new substitute for making the learning more beneficial for learners. Incorporation of cooperative learning into blended learning will make a new way of blended learning (Yen and Lee, 2011; Liu, 2010).

Why Blended Learning?

Blended learning is required in the present scenario in many ways. In the 21st century, life is so fast and every one of us wants to learn according to its ease and requirement, anywhere anytime. So blended learning is very useful in this way. The following points will highlight the need of Blended learning: -

1. Blended learning helps in boosting learners' efficiency. Learners can get learning material wherever and whenever required according to their ease, which motivates them to work efficiently.
2. Blended learning helps in engaging the learners in learning. By engaging the learners in learning, teachers can assess easily and make the learning very enjoyable to learners.
3. Through blended learning teachers can communicate easily with the learners by using technology and also in a traditional setting.
4. It helps the learners to learn collaboratively, discuss with one another, solve their doubts and give feedback for improvement in learning.

5. Blended learning helps in fulfilling the needs of every individual learner, by providing various audio-visual aids, ppts, images, etc.
6. It also helps in tracking the learner's progress through various online and offline assessment strategies.

Models Of Blended Learning:

According to Christensen, Horn, & Staker, (2013), in a blended learning program one out of the following four models are used: -

1. Rotation Model:

- A. The Station Rotation Model
 - B. Lab Rotation Model
 - C. Flipped Classroom
 - D. Individual Rotation
2. Flex Model
 3. A La Carte Model
 4. Enriched Virtual Model

Each model has its own importance and applicability according to the need and demand of the learning setup.

Rotation Model: In this model of blended learning, in teaching a particular subject students are rotated on a fixed schedule.

- A. **The Station Rotation Model:** - In a station rotation model, within a given course or subject, students are divided into different groups. The teacher fixed some learning stations i.e., online learning, individual tutoring, project work, assignment, etc. students rotate at fixed points in time between these different learning stations. In the Station Rotation model, students rotate through all of the stations.
 - B. **Lab Rotation Model:** - In a lab Rotation model, students rotate at fixed points in time between a classroom and computer lab. Students learn online in the computer lab, whereas they are involved in various types of activities in the classroom.
 - C. **Flipped Classroom:** - In this model of blended learning, the instructional or teachable content is given beforehand to students and still available in class.
 - D. **Individual Rotation:** - In this model of blended learning while learning the content, every student has an individualized playlist and does not necessarily rotate to each available station.
1. **Flex Model:** - In the Flex model, online learning is at the center of students' learning.

Students have a flexible schedule for their learning based on their needs and fixed goals. Students get online learning experiences as well as offline face-to-face learning experiences. Face-to-face learning experiences are given through discussion, projects, mentoring, tutoring, etc.; most of the learning takes place online.

2. **A La Carte Model:** - this model of blended learning allows the learner to take an online course with an online teacher in addition to their face-to-face learning which provides more flexibility in learning for students.
3. **Enriched Virtual Model:** - In the enriched virtual model of blended learning the student does not need to attend full-time classes in school. Students can complete the majority of their work online and they have to come to school for only face-to-face requirements of the course. In this model of learning daily attendance in schools is not required. Learners have to come only twice a week for face-to-face work learning.

Components Of Blended Learning:

1. Face-to-face teaching
2. Virtual classroom
3. Online learning
4. Mobile learning

5. Self-paced e-learning

6. Social learning/ informal learning

Blended Learning With Various Cooperative Learning Strategies:

There are various cooperative learning strategies that can help in boosting the learning in blended mode and make learning beneficial for learners:

1. Brainstorming
2. Crossover
3. Fishbowl
4. Think –Pair-Share CLS
5. Jigsaw CLS

There are many cooperative learning strategies available. Some cooperative learning strategies help in student pairing, while others help in small groups of four or five students.

Significance Of The Study

In this era of the 21st century, the traditional face-to-face teaching alone may not be proved most effective. It will be important to ponder upon how students learn best, and how we can improve their learning through cooperative and interactive strategies of learning because we want to educate the future generations. Blended learning takes an initiative in enhancing the traditional classroom setting and providing opportunities to participate in cooperative learning activities based on team-based projects and games in the classroom at various levels. With this paper, the author wants to merge blended learning with various cooperative learning strategies in order to broaden the horizons of the teaching-learning process in the future and to make learning more beneficial and interactive.

Objectives

1. Relevance of Blended Learning in the present scenario
2. Use of blended learning with various cooperative learning strategies

Research Methodology

We have used the content analysis technique to analyze the content and information regarding the Pedagogy, Blended Learning. For this we have gone through various journals, books and related articles & many more.

Implications Of The Paper:

The following will be the implications of this paper:

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1. Blended learning will Offer students the flexibility of time and with this learning outcomes will be improved
2. Blended learning will help in more student-teacher interaction
3. With blended learning students as well as teachers will attain more technological knowledge and this will increase their confidence in using new technologies
4. By using blended learning with cooperative learning strategies, there will be an increase in student engagement in the learning process

5. This study will benefit students, curriculum planners, teachers, and teacher's educators because switching from a traditional competition classroom to a cooperative learning method in a blended mode will be most beneficial in making learning more interactive and enjoyable.

Benefits Of Using Blended Learning In Teaching Learning Situations

1. In blended learning there will be maximum use of the technologies and other resources which will make individuals more techno-friendly
2. Through a blended mode of learning issues regarding distance are eliminated
3. Blended learning enables communication with all students.
4. Continuous feedback from the teacher as well as students will result in effective learning
5. Online resources are updated and upgraded from time to time. Thus, students have access to unlimited up-to-date resources
6. Blended learning helps to develop time management skills and critical thinking skill among students as well as teachers

Challenges To Be Faced While Using Blended Mode Of Learning

1. Blended mode of teaching and learning is very time-consuming:
2. Blended mode of teaching-learning needs extra efforts from teachers.
3. In blended learning students sometimes feel that they are given more work to do when distance modes are used.
4. Blended learning is dependent on technical resources and online information. These tools need to be reliable, easy to use, and updated in order to give a meaningful learning experience.
5. Blended learning needs a stable and adequate internet connection. The school or the institution should have adequate infrastructure and all facilities required for computer-based instruction.

Conclusion

Blended Learning is an important part of the future of the education system. It will provide students the flexibility of learning which will enhance the learning outcomes. Blended learning opens ways for many learners who were not able to get an education because of various physical barriers. With the knowledge of using technology in the classroom, both teachers and students will develop skills important for the 21st century. A blended mode of learning will enhance the critical thinking among the learners which will help them in the future. Thus, by using the blended mode of learning with the use of cooperative learning strategies will enhance the productivity in the learning environment.

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